

DISCUSSION

Beryllium chloride reacts freely with molten mono- and dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids and normal salts are formed. The reaction proceeds with the evolution of HCl till one of the reactants is exhausted.

In the case of monocarboxylic acids, such as lauric, myristic, palmitic, stearic and benzoic acids, one molecule of BeCl_2 reacts with two molecules of the acid with formation of the corresponding salt.

With molten sebacic and phthalic acids, which contain two carboxyl groups, the reaction is more vigorous and is completed in a comparatively short time. In this case one molecule of BeCl_2 reacts with only one molecule of the acid.

The hydroxy-acids, e. g., malic, citric and salicylic, react vigorously with BeCl_2 and the corresponding beryllium salts are formed with evolution of HCl, hydrogen of the hydroxyl and carboxyl groups being displaced in all the cases.

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CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART V. PHENOXIDES OF BERYLLIUM

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Beryllium phenoxides of α -naphthol, β -naphthol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, catechol, resorcinol, hydroquinone and pyrogallol have been prepared and their constitution discussed. Viscometric studies of the systems BeCl_2 - β -naphthol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, BeCl_2 -catechol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and BeCl_2 -pyrogallol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ have also been made.

Fricke and Havestadt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 146, 121) obtained impure beryllium phenoxide. Funke and Rogler (*ibid.*, 1944, 252, 323) prepared beryllium phenoxide by the interaction of BeCl_2 and phenol, and washing out excess of phenol with carbon tetrachloride. Silber (*Ann. Chim.*, 1952, 7, 182), however, observed that beryllium phenoxide was readily obtained by the reaction of phenols and beryllium chloride in boiling benzene with the evolution of HCl and separation of the phenoxide.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of BeCl_2 with phenol and the preparation of phenoxides of beryllium with mono-, di- and tri-hydroxyphenols.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium chloride was prepared as reported in Part IV (this issue, p. 261).

α -Naphthol, β -naphthol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol or resorcinol (double the requisite quantity in each case) was dissolved in benzene and BeCl_2 added to it. The content

was heated on a water-bath till the evolution of HCl had ceased. With α - and β -naphthols and *m*-cresol, a compound separated out in each case. With *o*-cresol no product separated; in this case benzene was distilled off when the residue left behind became insoluble in benzene. The compounds obtained were washed with benzene and dried in vacuum. They were further washed with dry ether, dried and analysed. In the case of resorcinol, a very small quantity of the phenoxide mixed with BeCl₂ was obtained.

Resorcinol, catechol, pyrogallol or hydroquinone was dissolved in dry ether and an ethereal solution of BeCl₂ was added to it. The mixture was gently warmed on an oil-bath till whole of the ether was evaporated off. The temperature of the oil-bath was then raised 10–20° above the m.p. of the respective phenol, and heating continued till HCl had ceased to evolve. The product obtained in each case was washed repeatedly with dry ether, dried and analysed.

In the case of solid phenols, alternative synthesis was carried out by heating phenols and BeCl₂ at a temperature of 10–12° higher than the m.p. of the respective phenol. The reaction took unusually long time for completion (sometime more than 48 hours). In all the cases the reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. The compounds obtained in these cases were identical with those obtained in benzene or ether except in the case of α -naphthol, where a compound having an indefinite composition was obtained.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured (except *o*-cresoxide which is white). They are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. They decompose when treated with dilute acids and alkalis. Beryllium resorcinoxide is soluble in dilute NH₄OH and NaOH; from the former, the compound may be recovered undecomposed.

The compounds were analysed by methods described in Part IV (*loc. cit.*). In a few cases carbon and hydrogen were estimated.

TABLE I

Phenols.	% Beryllium.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Colour.
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
α -Naphthol	3.07	3.05	...	...	...	...	Dark brown
β -Naphthol	3.08	3.05	...	...	...	...	Ash
<i>o</i> -Cresol	7.72	7.83	73.10	73.04	5.17	5.21	White
<i>m</i> -Cresol	7.79	7.83	73.09	73.04	5.19	5.21	Pink
Catechol	7.70	7.69	...	...	...	...	Black
Resorcinol	7.64	7.69	...	...	...	...	Light brown
Hydroquinone	7.65	7.69	...	...	...	...	Black
Pyrogallol	6.77	6.77	54.00	54.13	3.11	3.00	Black

DISCUSSION

Beryllium chloride forms stable complex compounds with water and alcohol (Fricke and Ruschhaupt, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 150, 103; Fricke and Havestadt, *loc. cit.*). The co-ordinate link is through the oxygen atom which acts as the donor.

On mixing ethereal solution of β -naphthol and BeCl_2 , although no compound separated out, HCl gas evolved slowly which became more pronounced on warming, indicating an interaction between phenol and BeCl_2 .

Naphthols and cresols react readily with BeCl_2 in benzene. Practically the whole of BeCl_2 was changed to beryllium phenoxides; but in the case of resorcinol, a very small quantity of phenoxide mixed with practically the whole of the unchanged BeCl_2 was obtained. This is similar to Silber's observation (*loc. cit.*) who found that the solubility of phenol in benzene was responsible for the reaction.

Naphthols and cresols, which are highly soluble in benzene, form phenoxides readily and the reaction proceeds to completion. Resorcinol, which is sparingly soluble, yields only a small quantity of impure phenoxide.

In the case of α - and β -naphthols, two molecules of phenols combine with one molecule of BeCl_2 forming the phenoxides, represented as :

When the reaction is carried out at 10 - 15° above the m.p. of catechol, resorcinol or hydroquinone, it reacts readily with BeCl_2 , and pure phenoxide is obtained in each case. In all these cases one molecule of phenol reacts with a molecule of BeCl_2 with evolution of HCl .

In the case of pyrogallol, only two hydrogen atoms are displaced from the three hydroxyl groups present and the compound is similar to the compounds obtained with dihydroxyphenols. As experiments could not be performed to show which of the two hydrogen atoms takes part in the reaction, no definite structure can be assigned to this compound.

It is interesting to note that one molecule of *o*- or *m*-cresol reacts with one of beryllium chloride although cresols contain only one hydroxyl group. *o*-Cresoxide formed remained dissolved in benzene solution whereas *m*-cresoxide separated out as in the case of α - and β -naphthoxides. From these results it is evident that the methyl group also takes part in the reaction with the ring-closure. It seems probable that the hydroxyl group reacts first with the formation of an intermediate compound ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O}\cdot\text{BeCl}_2$) which undergoes orientation and a ring-closure takes place with the evolution of a further molecule of HCl . The reactions can be represented as

Viscosity of the systems BeCl_2 -catechol-EtOH, BeCl_2 - β -naphthol-EtOH and BeCl_2 -pyrogallol-EtOH was studied, but no indication of the formation of any complex compound was observed in each case.

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